

The Diasporic Experience in Contemporary Indian Cinema

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Abstract The Indian diaspora is possibly the fastest-growing one in the world. It is roughly estimated at 11 million- 1.7 million in Europe with about 1.2 million in Great Britain, 2.8 million in Africa, 4.2 million in the Middle East and 2.7 million in the United States among other countries. Indian Diaspora is now an important market of popular Hindi cinema and through this, a large number of people are experiencing it in day-to-day life. Popular Hindi cinema has been a major factor in recreating India abroad. Bollywood films have a wide viewership overseas and are seen not only on home videos and cable but also in cinema halls. Bollywood cinema plays a central role in the negotiation of national identity. The Non-Resident Indians (NRIs) shown in the films become the epitome of Indianness and embody both Western modernity and Eastern traditionalism. The viewers of Bollywood cinema, in India as well as abroad, who do not know much about the term 'diaspora' experience it nevertheless through these movies. They get familiar with the ways of identity crisis, the struggle of immigrants, nostalgia and the politics of the government abroad through these Bollywood movies. They also experience the struggle of immigrants as victims of racism, economic exploitation and a legal system beyond their comprehension. The thrust of the paper is to present the diasporic experience and nostalgia in contemporary films, namely, *Namaste London*, *Pardes* and *Swades*.

Keywords Diaspora, Identity, Cinema, Nostalgia, Immigration.

Introduction

Popular Hindi Cinema has grown enormously in its visibility over the past decades, not only within the context of India but also on a global stage. It plays a central role in the preparation of the national Identity, so much so that "film is perhaps the single strongest agency for the creation of national mythology of heroism, consumerism, leisure and sociality." (Appadurai & Breckenridge 8) Because of its key role in the creation of national identity and its place in the collective imagination it constitutes an interesting area of study. As Ashish Nandy noted "the popular film is low-brow, modernizing India in all its complexity, sophistry, naiveté and vulgarity. Studying popular film is studying Indian modernity at its rawest, its crudities laid bare by the fate of traditions in contemporary life and arts. Above all, it is studying caricatures of ourselves." (Nandy 7)

Aim of study

Directors, producers, distributors, and the Censor Board collectively aim to produce content that is both commercially successful and socially acceptable, while also possessing aesthetic appeal. This shared objective significantly influences and reflects societal perspectives on national identity, gendered behavior, and acceptable norms. Popular cinema plays a vital role in the process of social engineering.

Hall characterizes the New World as not just a physical place but also a narrative of displacement, leading to an intense imaginative richness that evokes a strong longing to reconnect with "lost origins." However, this desire for a return mirrors Lacan's concept of the imaginary, as it is unattainable and unrewardable. It signifies the commencement of the symbolic realm, involving representation, and functions as an endlessly renewable wellspring of desire, memory, myth, exploration, and revelation—essentially constituting the foundation of our cinematic narratives.

Review of Literature

Popular Hindi cinema plays a major role in recreating India abroad and recreates its own version of the diaspora; as Vijay Mishra says that "Yash Chopra's *Lamhe* (1991), though not exactly about the diaspora, makes a point that diasporic subjects are not bound by Indian social norms." (Mishra 249) Mishra also considers *Dilwale Dulhania Le Jayenge* as a "seminal text about diasporic representation and consumption of Indian popular culture" and is of the view that its success in the Indian diaspora is due "to the ways in which it re-projects the diasporic subject by first internalizing him or her." (Mishra 250)

The east/west binary can be seen in Vipul Amrutlal Shah's *Namastey London*. The film offers intriguing insights into the hypocrisy of Non-Resident Indians, who raise their children as product of their new environment. The film tries to show the conflicts between the generation of Non-Resident Indians born in India and their British-born and raised children.

Main Text

The movie starts with a song which is *Main jahan rahun... main kahin bhi rahun... teri yaad saath hai*, represents a very strong affection for India. Here in the lyrics the word 'teri' refers to India. The whole song portrays India and London alternatively and hence this movie proves to be of great importance in the Indian Diaspora's identity constructs.

Jasmeet Malhotra or Jazz is the only daughter of Manmohan Malhotra, a fun-loving, young working lady who enjoys partying. She has a sense of independence and prefers to be known as a British as she was born and brought up in London. She even thinks of herself as British and wants to marry a man of British origin. When her friend Laila asks what are you? You are an Indian too! Then she replies "I am British. I was not born in India. My parents are the citizens of London... I was born and brought up here. Therefore, my attitude, my thinking, my likings are all British." (*Namastey London*)

Manmohan decides to take her to India and wants to get her married to an Indian groom. He knows that her daughter will never agree to such an idea so he gives her an offer to take her to India under the pretence of a holiday trip so they can have shots of The Taj Mahal, Delhi, Jaipur, Ajmer Sharif, Haridwar, Rishikesh, Kedarnath etc. The visit to these monuments and places of leisure coincides with pre-arranged meetings with families of and prospective Indian grooms. The visit however fails to play up to Manmohan's expectations.

Finally, Manmohan takes her to his ancestral village in Punjab. We see here the cultural stereotypes of a traditional combined Indian family. Here Jasmeet meets a young Punjabi farmer boy Arjun, who is the son of Manmohan's childhood friend. Manmohan almost immediately decides to get his daughter married off to Arjun after meeting him. Jasmeet doesn't want to marry Arjun and tries to run off to London but her friend Imran advises her not to run. So she is forced into a marriage with Arjun, who is very different from her. After returning to London she dumps her husband Arjun for her British-origin boyfriend Charlie Brown, by saying that her marriage in India is not legal in London. Not one to be defeated, Arjun decides to win her heart before she weds to Charles. Jasmeet does get engaged to Charles and it is when Jasmeet and Arjun spend time together as friends, Jasmeet falls in love with Arjun.

Arjun stands for India's culture and modesty. On the day of Jasmeet's engagement to Charles in London when Mister John Pringle ridicules Jasmeet's nickname "Jazz" and India and refers to it as a Land of snake charmers and rope tricksters, Arjun comes to him and represents India by greeting "Namastey" and says that, "When we greet one another, we fold our hand in Namastey because we believe that God resides in the heart of every human being. We come from a nation where we allow a lady of Catholic origin to step aside for a Sikh to be sworn in as Prime Minister by a Muslim President to govern a nation of over 80 per cent Hindus. It may also interest you to know that many of the origins of your words come from Sanskrit. For Example, maatr becomes mother, bhratr becomes brother, giamiti becomes geometry, trikonmiti becomes trigonometry. We have 5600 newspapers, and 35000 magazines in over twenty-one different languages with a combined readership of over 120 million. We have reached the moon and back but yet you people still feel that we've only reached as far as the Indian rope trick. We are the third largest nation in the world of doctors, engineers and Scientists. We have the third largest army in the world and even then I fold my hands in humility before you because we don't believe that we are above or beneath any Individual." (*Namastey London*)

One of the incidents in the film which represents the generation gap and nostalgia is when Jasmeet leaves by saying "If I have to live my life my way, then I must also find myself another accommodation...." On this, Manmohan gets offensive and turns his anger to his wife by questioning the upbringing of Jasmeet. He even blames her for Jasmeet's Westernized behaviour which she defends by saying that she did not want her daughter to be ridiculed (the way she had been by her husband) and brought her up as a Londoner so that Manmohan wouldn't feel embarrassed to take her daughter out with him in public

(as he feels in case of her wife). At last, Manmohan says "I am just the Indian father of an English daughter" when confronted with his daughter's Westernized life. This shows the disappointment of a father because of cultural diversity and the generation gap.

Manmohan had married on a trip to India, left her wife there for four years and then called her to London. Thus a simple village girl from Punjab is thrust into an alien land, asked to speak English and said to be dressed like the westerners, and her attempt to try to include all this into her new life is often criticized by her husband. Another track in the film which shows the Diaspora and cultural gap is Imran, a Pakistani origin Jasmeet's friend, who is also born and brought up in London like Jasmeet. He is in love with a Christian lady Suzanne, which also upsets his parents and his story follows a pattern similar to that of Jasmeet.

The film is full of dialogues which accentuate India's greatness and point out cultural differences between the East and West. The main concern of the movie is the generational and cultural gap between the father and daughter and the confusion present in modern-day relationships. Apart from a romantic comedy, the film is also about identities that are confused and insecure. The film also depicts that home and identity are very essential in one's life as Manmohan comes to India to find and re-acquaint with his roots.

Subhash Ghai's *Pardes* is all about the beauty and worthiness of Indian culture and values which in this movie is been contrasted with Western culture and values of America. Kishorilal, who is a rich Indian businessman living in America, visits for the first time in ten years to his childhood friend Suraj Dev in India. Kishorilal sees Ganga, the only daughter of Suraj Dev and is impressed with her. Then he decides to get his son Rajiv married to Ganga. Ganga is the mirror image of India's cultural values and traditions. In the film, the word "Ganga" is used as a symbol concerning the Holy River in India which is known for its cultural importance. As we see in a scene when Kishorilal goes back to America and tells everyone about Ganga then Krishna Didi says "You did right but Kishorilal! Do you know that you're trying to bring India's holy Ganga to Isolated America?" Kishorilal defends by saying that I am bringing her to protect India's race, culture and civilization in America.

The film is laced with traditional folk songs *Suhaag Maangan Jaye Banni* and *Ghumdat Aave Suhaag More Angne* which represents the hard-core cultural aspect of India. The song, in which Western-clothed Kishorilal returns in Kurta and Pajama and sings the song *Ye Mera India... I Love My India*, presents a nationalistic overtone. Various Indian landmarks such as the birthplace of Lord Krishna and the Red Fort are shown in this song. Displaying deities such as Lord Krishna and mentioning that "God lives [in India]" shows India's spiritual significance as well. The overall song serves to reinforce the notion that India is also culturally superior to other countries.

Like Jasmeet in *Namastey London*, Rajiv is the Westernized son of Kishorilal, hates India and its culture and represents the second-generation Diaspora, who is more concerned about America than India. Kishorilal knows that it's hard to convince Rajiv to marry or even meet Ganga. Back in America, Kishorilal asks Arjun, who is his adopted but Indian-born son and works in Kishorilal's garage. Unlike Rajiv, Arjun was born in India and despite his American residence; he still maintains a love and respect for India. Arjun is a musician and true to his Indo-philic nature, is also the writer of *the I Love My India* song. Arjun comes to India before Rajiv and creates favourable situations for him. Rajiv still gets confused so he wants Ganga to experience American life before marriage. Both get engaged and fly off to America where Ganga faces a kind of cultural shock. Rajiv doesn't treat Ganga as her expectations had her believing and ignores her while Arjun tries her best to make Ganga's visit as pleasurable as possible. Despite Arjun's best efforts, Ganga notices Rajiv's vices and at this point, Ganga and Arjun develop a strong bond that some, including Kishorilal, consider as love. Kishorilal sends Rajiv and Ganga to enjoy and spend a good time in Las Vegas. Rajiv drinks there and tries to exploit Ganga when Ganga forces him not to do so he shocks her by labelling Indians as hypocrites. Rajiv exclaims, "You bloody Indians start whining and crying when someone mentions the word 'sex' yet you Indians manage to have the world's [second] largest population! Such hypocrisy!" and further says that "Your India is nothing but a shit." (*Pardes*) Being the courageous woman Ganga fights him off and escapes from his lustful wrath. This scene shows the anti-Indian attitude of second-generation children.

Ganga runs off to India with Arjun and the whole story is narrated to Ganga's family by Kishorilal. Ganga's father believes the story and tries to kill Arjun and Ganga, as he considers Ganga the reason for defaming the family's name. Kishorilal and Rajiv fly back to India to bring back Ganga and act offensively but Ganga denies it and explains the whole story. At last, in response to all this drama Kishorilal decides that only Arjun can marry Ganga; his biological son has been too polluted by the Western world to deserve such a purge gem like Ganga.

Kishorilal's character in the film shows a kind of displacement where on one hand he does not want to leave America for fame, wealth and opportunities and on the other hand he also does not want to detach from his roots and culture in India.

Set in contemporary times, Ashutosh Gowariker's *Swades* also looks at the issue of the Indian Diaspora, the return to one's roots, a feeling of lack of traditional bonds and a sense of community in the fragmented American society. The subtitle "*We, the people*" suggests the unity of identities and a sense of personal responsibility.

Mohan Bhargava is a Non-Resident Indian working as a Project Manager at NASA. He comes to India to take Kaveri Amma along with him. Kaveri Amma is the woman who was his dai and looked after him when he was growing up. In the process of pursuing Kaveri Amma, Mohan spends three weeks in India and develops a sense of attachment to the village and its people. During these three weeks, he experiences the harsher aspects of the village like poverty, caste discrimination, child marriage, illiteracy and child labour. He tries his way to bring about some changes. He with the help of voluntary labour builds a small hydroelectric power plant that generates electricity. In doing this, he earns the respect of village people. Kaveri Amma refuses to come with him forcing his lone return home but what retains is a growing sense of responsibility towards the village and guilt for not being able to do much for the welfare of its people. At last, he finishes his project at NASA, resigns there and returns to India.

Conclusion

All these movies portray India's culture, tradition, ethnicity and sense of nationalism through the narratives, songs, dialogues and the mannerism of the characters even though they have been brought up under varied circumstances, but a search for identity, an inherent longing for familiarity and security unites them as one and renders them as a whole.

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